

IN VITRO SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF CLINICAL ISOLATES OF YEAST AND YEAST LIKE FUNGI TO VARIOUS EXTRACTS OF *JATROPHA CURCAS*

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ABSTRACT

Background: There has been a growing need for more antifungal drugs while the resistance of antifungal drugs as well has been on the increase; also there has been long established medicinal potentials ascribed to *Jatropha curcas*.

Objective: To establish antifungal properties present in the extracts of *J. curcas*.

Methods: Various fungi were isolated from clinical samples. Potato dextrose agar and Sabouraud dextrose agar were prepared to grow the fungi. *J. curcas* extracts were obtained by various methods: crude, water, methanol and lyophilization; both the crude and processed extracts were tested against selected fungi in various concentrations of v/v 5%, 10% and 15%, and their minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) were established using break point plate and tube methods. Results obtained were analysed using simple descriptive methods.

Results: *Trichophyton mentagrophyte*, *Trichophyton verrucosum*, *Trichosporon beigelii*, and *Candida albicans* were found to be highly susceptible to the seed and seed testa extracts of *J. curcas* while *Aspergillus fumigatus* was resistant to all the extracts tested.

Conclusion: The safe and achievable plasma levels of these extracts should be established as well as ascertain the toxic and other side effects of the extracts so that this antifungal potential could be properly exploited for human benefit.

KEY WORDS: *Jatropha curcas*; Extracts; Susceptibility; Fungi.

INTRODUCTION

Fungi have generally been linked with infections in man for quite a long time (Amanuel, *et al*, 2001; Fornadley, *et al*, 1990; Grant, and Armatrong, 1988; and, de Repentigney, *et al*, 2004), however, this association with man has attained an unprecedented increase over the past one and a half decade (Moore and Chaisson, 1996; Pons, *et al*, 1993; Cauda, *et al*, 1999; and, Sangeorzan, *et al*, 1994). The technological breakthrough and advancement in medical technology on one hand (Fon-Havard, *et al*, 1991; and, Vonden-Bossche, *et al*, 1994), and the dreaded HIV acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) (Rhunke, *et al*, 1994; and, Maenza, *et al*, 1997) on the other have all contributed to the current upsurge of fungal infections (Chavanet, *et al*, 1994; and, Girmenia, *et al*, 2000).

The current increase in the use of antifungal drugs, both for therapeutic and prophylactic purposes has sparked up a resistance phenomenon which has similarly been on the increase (Boschmen, *et al*, 1998; and, Silva, *et al*, 1998). In a study carried out in Cambodia (Alexander, and Perfect, 1997; Lewis, and Klepser, 1999; and, Sar, *et al*, 2004) on 402 isolates of *Cryptococcus neoformans* from cerebrospinal fluid samples; resistance against fluconazole increased by over 500% over a 12 months period of its continuous use. Findings from another study on various species of *Candida* in Italy (Barchiesi, *et al*, 1999) showed that, *C. lusitania* and *C. lipolytica* were highly resistant to flucytosine (33% to 50%); while in another study carried

Table 1 Preliminary screening (without control) of the effects of the crude extracts of *Jatropha curcas* on some fungi using different extraction methods.

Water Extract

Concentration (v/v %)	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophyte</i>					<i>Trichophyton verrucosum</i>				
	LV	RT	SP	SD	ST	LV	RT	SP	SD	ST
5%	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
10%	R	R	R	S	S	R	R	R	S	S
15%	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R

	<i>Trichosporon beigelii</i>					<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>				
	LV	RT	SP	SD	ST	LV	RT	SP	SD	ST
5%	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
10%	R	R	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R
15%	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R

	<i>Candida albicans</i>				
	LV	RT	SP	SD	ST
5%	R	R	R	R	R
10%	R	R	R	S	S
15%	R	R	R	R	R

out in Germany (Muller, *et al*, 2000), it was observed that an azole cross-resistance to ketoconazole, fluconazole, itraconazole, and voriconazole among clinical isolates of *Candida albicans* was common. The resistance of several antifungal drugs is believed to be associated with microsomal cytochrome P-450 content of the fungal cells; it leads to subcellular ergosterol synthesis from membrane or lanosterol (Dyer, *et al*, 2000). Findings from Belgium (Bossche, *et al*, 1992) showed that, resistance increased with the level of P-450-dependent 14 alpha-demethylation of lanosterol and also increased ergosterol synthesis was correspondingly seen in intact fungal cells which coincided with their increased resistance against the azoles and amphotericin B. These resistant cells also had a correspondingly high concentration of squalene epoxidase activity needed to convert squalene to 2,3-oxidosqualene.

As the build up of resistance among fungi continues (Hoban, *et al*, 1999; Pfaller, *et al*, 1998; Rodero, *et al*, 1996; and, van Duin, *et al*, 2004), there is need for newer generic antifungal drugs with the added advantage of high efficacy, wide spectrum of activity and with inherent slow onset of resistance to be released to replace the fading ones (Diz-Dios, *et al*, 2001; and, Pearson, *et al*, 2003). This would strengthen and sustain the current supportive management of patients with especially HIV AIDS and other immunosuppressive ailments (de Repentigny, *et al*, 1996; Agresti, *et al*, 1994; Powderly, *et al*, 1994; and, Bertagnolio, *et al*, 2004). The fact that, at present, at least 4 billion of the world's population is at the risk of contracting HIV infection, predominantly from Sub-saharan Africa, other tropical and sub-tropical parts of the world; and about 60% of these stand the risk of going down with AIDS with associated fungal opportunistic infections (Lamprey, *et al*, 2006; UNAIDS, 2006; Bridge, 2006; and, Dzekedzeke, and Flykesneg, 2006); the need for a continuous search for more antifungal drugs becomes imperative.

Methanol Extract (Seed only)

<i>T. mentagrophyte</i>	<i>T. verrucosum</i>	<i>T. beigelii</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
S	S	S	R	S

Key: LV=Leaves, RT=Roots, SP=Sap, SD=Seed, ST=Seed Testa, R=Resistant, S=Susceptible.

Table 2 Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of the various extracts of *J. curcas* on selected fungi.

Fungi	E Lyophilized (mg/ml)	X Methanol (Seed)(mg/m)	T Seed Testa (mg/ml)
<i>T. mentagrophyte</i>	10	32	88
<i>T. verrucosum</i>	20	24	56
<i>T. beigelii</i>	10	36	72
<i>C. albicans</i>	10	40	104

Jatropha curcas commonly called Barbados nuts in English is a tall shrub that grows commonly in different parts of the world (*Jatropha curcas*, 2006). Its leaves are prepared with soup in India, while in Southern Sudan, the seeds as well as the fruits are used as contraceptive (Gaydon, *et al*, 1982; and, Watt, and Breyer-Brandwijk, 1962). Its medicinal value has been widely exploited traditionally in the past for various ailments with arguable successes (Morton, 1977; and, Swarbrick, 1997).

This study was set up to ascertain the antifungal properties inherent in various extracts of *J. curcas*; the findings would lead to the discovery of possibly another potent antifungal drug in this critical period of antifungal therapy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Setting The study was carried out at the Microbiology laboratory of the National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI) Vom, Plateau state between September and December 2005.

Collection of Sap Pasteur pipette was used to collect sap of the plant. The sap was collected at the buds of the plant by plucking off the leaf; the samples were placed in bijoux bottles and stored in the refrigerator at 8°C.

Extraction of Seed Testa Ten grams of ground dry sample of the seed testa was weighed and soaked in 100ml of water overnight using beakers. The sample was filtered and the extracts obtained were stored in a refrigerator at 8°C in reagent bottles.

Extraction of the leaves and Root Bark of *J. curcas* The leaves were sun dried and ground to powder, 10 grams of the ground dry samples of the leaves were weighed and soaked in 100ml of clean water overnight using beaker. Another set of 10 grams of the sample were soaked in 100ml of distilled water and boiled for 30 minutes. The samples were filtered and the extracts obtained were stored in refrigerator in reagent bottles at 8°C.

Extraction of the Crude Extracts of the Seeds - The seeds of the plant were washed and dried; 10grams of the dried and crushed seeds were soaked in 100ml of water and boiled for 30 minutes. The extracted oil was filtered and stored in refrigerator at 4°C in reagent bottles.

Soxhlet Extraction of Seed- The solvent used was absolute methanol. 20g of the ground dry sample of the seed was placed in an extracting thimble and placed in the soxhlet apparatus. A water condenser was attached to the soxhlet apparatus at the top. The apparatus was fitted into the neck of a flask containing 250mls of the methanol (solvent) heated on a water bath.

The vapour from the solvent reached the soxhlet apparatus through the side tube and condensed on passing into the condenser. The condensed solvent dropped on the crude substance in the thimble and dissolved the required substance. The solution filtered through the thimble into the flask bearing the solvent. This process continued until the solvent from the thimble was colourless. Extraction was then said to be completed. This continuous extraction method extracted all the components of the plant which were soluble in methanol. The extract was then evaporated to dryness and a light yellow oily extract was collected, weighed and stored by refrigeration for further susceptibility testing.

Lyophilization- Two mls of 10% concentration each of the different hot water extract were dispensed into vaccine bottles and taken into the lyophilizer for freeze-drying. This served as a means of storage of the extracts as well as their concentration. The lyophilized extracts were weighed and incorporated into the agar medium (sabouraud dextrose agar) and their MICs determined subsequently.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing- The culture media used were Sabouraud dextrose agar and Potato dextrose agar which were prepared based on the manufacturers specifications. Organisms used in the study were obtained from clinical samples at Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH) using standard laboratory procedures (Baron, *et al*, 1994). The susceptibility method used was the agar plate minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) method. Various known volumes of the extract were added into the melted Sabouraud dextrose agar medium in desired concentrations of 5%, 10% and 15%; the agar medium was then poured into plates and tubes and allowed to solidify. The solid plates were surface inoculated with the following fungi: *Candida albicans*, *Trichophyton mentagrophyte*, *Trichophyton verrucosum*, *Trichosporon beigeli* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*. All were incubated at room temperature of 25°C to 28°C except *Candida albicans* which was incubated at 36.5°C, and growth was observed on alternate days for a period of 7 to 21 days maximum. Control tubes and plates were set up with and without incorporating the extracts and also inoculated with the same organisms. The 5%, 10%, and 15% concentration of the extracts were used in the dose ranges of 0.1 to 1.8mls. The MICs were calculated as follow:

MIC of Methanol Extract: 1ml of 10% concentration= 400mg
Volume of Sabouraud Dextrose agar = 10ml
Hence, Final concentration = 40mg/ml

MIC of Lyophilized Extract: 2ml of Extract= 0.2g= Weight of Powder per 2ml
1ml= 0.1g= 100mg
Volume of culture medium in test tube = 10ml
Hence, Final Concentration of Extract= 10mg/ml

MIC of Seed testa Extract: 1 ml of 10% concentration of seed testa extract = 800mg
Volume of Agar= 10 ml
Hence, Final concentration = 80mg/ml

Interpretation of Results- The results were interpreted based on- the smallest amount of the test agent that inhibited visible growth, visible growth or its absence in the negative control or absence of visible growth in all the media as follows:

Sensitive- Presence of visible growth in the negative control but no growth in some levels of concentration in the test sample.

Resistant- Presence of visible growth in the negative control along with all levels of concentration in the test sample.

Fungi Dead- Absence of growth in both positive and negative controls as well as test sample.

Analysis of Results: The results obtained were analysed using simple descriptive methods.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the preliminary screening of the effects of the crude extracts of *Jatropha curcas* on selected fungi. All the different concentrations (5%, 10% and 15%) of leaf, root bark, sap, seed and seed testa extracts of *J. curcas* were resistant to *Trichophyton mentagrophyte*, except the 10% v/v concentration of the seed and seed testa extracts which were sensitive against the organism. Similar susceptibility patterns were recorded with *Trichophyton verrucosum*, *Trichosporon beigelii* and *Candida albicans*. *Aspergillus fumigatus* on the other hand was resistant to all the various concentrations of the crude extracts of *J. curcas*. The methanol seed extracts of the tall shrub were sensitive against all the fungi tested except *Aspergillus fumigatus* which was resistant.

Table 2 shows the minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of the various extracts of *J. curcas* on selected fungi. The MICs of lyophilized extract (in mg/ml) for *T. mentagrophyte*, *T. verrucosum*, *T. beigelii*, and *C. albicans* were: 10, 20, 10, and 10 respectively; for methanol seed extract (in mg/ml) were: 32, 24, 36, and 40 respectively; and for the seed testa extract were (in mg/ml): 88, 56, 72, and 104 respectively.

DISCUSSION

T. mentagrophyte, *T. verrucosum*, *T. beigelii* and *C. albicans* were found to be highly susceptible to the crude extracts of the seed and seed testa of *J. curcas* while *A. fumigatus* was resistant to all the extracts tested. This antifungal property exhibited by *J. curcas* can be exploited in the development of a new antifungal drug. This would widen the scope of the present day antifungal therapy and increase the freedom of choice among antifungal drugs most especially in the current trend of antifungal resistance (Perkins, *et al*, 2005; and, Pfaller, *et al*, 2005).

The resistance shown by *A. fumigatus* against all the extracts could be a pointer to the fact that, there may be several other pathogenic fungi inherently resistant to this compound (Redding, *et al*, 1994) and these calls for the need to establish the antifungal spectrum of the extract (Peyron, *et al*, 2001).

The MICs of the extracts ranged from 10mg/ml to 104 mg/ml against different fungi; preparations for possible human consumption with the lowest possible MICs would be preferred especially in the treatment of HIV AIDS patients who might be on several other drugs concurrently; this would reduce the combined effect of consuming a large number of multiple drugs (Kartsonis, *et al*, 2004). The MICs from the present study are higher than that of: Girmenia *et al* (Girmenia, *et al*, 2000) who reported MIC 0.008mg/ml fluconazole against *C. albicans* and 0.000125mg/ml voriconazole against same; Muller *et al* (Muller, *et al*, 2000) who recorded the MICs of amphotericin B, itraconazole, ketoconazole and voriconazole in the range of 0.00003-0.016mg/ml and for fluconazole, 0.000125-0.064mg/ml from clinical isolates of oropharyngeal candidiasis. The high MIC recorded in the present study may be due to the fact that the extracts were still not yet in the refined form as compared to the other findings (Girmenia, *et al*, 2000). Also the methodology of susceptibility in the present study; though certified by the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards (NCCLS) for intra and interpersonal reproducibility; the more new certified methodologies appear to have an edge over it (Barchiesi, *et al*, 1999; and, Maxwell, *et al*, 2003).

Although the achievable and safe plasma levels of the extracts were not concurrently ascertained in the course of the study so as to guide on the proper interpretation of the susceptibility pattern; the susceptibility of fungi to these extracts nevertheless has been proven. This could however form the basis for further studies on the extracts and also identify possible toxic and other side effects.

In conclusion, the seed and seed testa extracts of *J. curcas* were found to be highly sensitive to several fungi tested. The extracts should therefore be prepared in more refined form so as to identify the active pharmacologic component, and also establish the safe and achievable plasma levels so as to help interpret its susceptibility patterns so that this antifungal potential could be properly exploited for human benefit.

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